

TOURISM TRADE AS THE ECONOMIC PHENOMENON IN DIFFERENT SCIENTIFIC FIELDS

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the export and trade of tourism not only in the economic sphere, but also in the social, humanitarian and other spheres, the impact of each sphere on the tourism trade, the role of psychological factors in growth dynamics, the relationship of all fields in the process of strategic choice.*

***Keywords:** tourism industry, psychological tourism, social tourism, locals and tourist behavior, tourism marketing, tourism strategies, 4Ps of tourism industry.*

Introduction

Tourism, the act and process of spending time away from home in pursuit of recreation, relaxation, and pleasure, while making use of the commercial provision of services [13].

Accounting for 10.3 % of world tourism GDP and 333 million global employment in 2019[14], tourism trade became one of the most up beating and important trade sectors. However, this statistics dropped till 6.2% and 289 million job opportunities respectively in 2021 due to COVID-19 global pandemic[14]. As the result, 4-5% of loss was seen by world tourism trade until the beginning of the 2022. From the numbers above we can see how much economically important phenomenon is tourism industry and learning it with the scope of many fields.

This article tries to analyze tourism trade in the terms of economy, marketing, sociology, psychology, geography and management.

Literature review

Economic growths has its requirements, including high share of international trade. In the terms of tourism trade, also we can see that the bigger share the better profit for the nation. For this purpose, learning trade from economic point of view is not enough. In order to achieve increase in tourism trade learning it from different fields view, for instance sociology, psychology, marketing and management will increase the potential understanding of trade strategy and make better plans for the upcoming chosen period.

Scientists like Cohen, D. Mackenel, D. Harrison, D. Burstin, D. Urry. S. Rojack[6] learned tourism from sociology prospective.

While A. Adler, J. Adler, J. Crompton, R. Crandell, J. Dann, R. Calanton, Vada, S., Prentice, C., Scott, N., & Hsiao, A. (2020)[12] learned tourism trade from psychological point of view.

Methodology

The base of this research methodology is the fundamental principles of economic theory and the works of leading local and foreign economists who have conducted research on the problem under study. The research also used methods such as theoretical observation, scientific abstraction, comparative analysis, and infographics.

Research and analyses

When the importance of tourism trade is explained, many scientists only see the economic aspects of tourism because it is easy to see it through calculations and statistics. From another

point of view, tourism trade has 7 different aspects which brings profit we want, also information for strategic planning. In scientific term we can see connection between tourism and 7 sciences. Tourism is learned by 7 different sciences: marketing, economy, sociology, archeology and geography, international law and most importantly information technology. It is obvious how much economic importance of tourism trade has in the economy, detailed economic importance and effect of it is explained in 1.3 chapter below. Starting from the **sociology**, many scientists learned sociologic importance of tourism trade, what is the connection between these 2 different sciences, how important is to open sociologic aspect of tourism trade.

The sociological approach includes numerous articles and individual scientific research of representatives of the sociology of tourism and travel S. Cohen, D. Mackenel, D. Harrison, D. Burstin, D. Urry. S. Rojack, W. Hannerza, J. Frow, N. Graberna. Sociological concepts of Ch. Mills, X. Ortega y Gasset, G. Marcuse, P. Sorokin, D. Bell, Z. Bauman, E. Gidtsens, containing a philosophical analysis of processes, associated with the phenomenon of travel and tourism. In the works of the above sociologists contain different interpretations of the influence of the phenomenon of tourism in sociocultural space at the regional, national and global levels[6]. Tourism is affected by any imbalances that arise in economic relations

Figure 1. Connection of tourism and other sciences *Source: made by author*

A major event in world social life or changes in the economic system will immediately reflect on the state and dynamics of tourism development. The Russian financial crisis of 1998 shook society. The Asian crisis had a bad effect on the tourism market of this region, and as a result, the dynamics of tourism decreased by 10%. Due to the global financial and economic crisis

that began in 2008, the flow of world tourism decreased by 8%. In constant development, tourism is considered as a social phenomenon. People's behavior is studied depending on their age, nationality, social status, education, place of residence, and cultural views.

Sociology learns 2 big following aspects of tourism:

➤ **Tourist and locals:** role of tourist, what makes them choose specific areas, why they travel and how they behave when ordinary person becomes a tourist. Tourists and their social impacts to local people and culture are learned by sociologists. Few studies deal specifically, however, with the nature and dynamics of the tourist-local relationship, which has three principal dimensions: people's interactions, perceptions and attitudes[2].

➤ **Phenomenon of tourism industry:** Sociology sees tourism industry as the part of nation which works to get profit also keeps its real role to improve its sociologic responsibilities. Socioeconomically, the system hinges on a group of national and increasingly transnational corporate actors and governmental and intergovernmental agencies, such as airlines; travel companies, travel agencies, and tour operators; hotel chains; international travel organizations[8].

Nowadays a lot of attention is paid to sociological research. At almost every major event, exhibition, a survey is conducted in order to collect various information from tourists and visitors. These questionnaires provide important information for assessing current and future travel levels. Sociological research data is the primary basis for the formation of policies for the movement of tourism products in a specific consumer market, the development of forecasts and guidelines, and the adoption of important political and economic decisions in the field of customs and migration relations and regulations. Within the framework of the psychological approach, a certain interest in the light of the study motivation and travel needs represent work E. Fromm. Problems of motivation of tourists, classification of tourists by psychographic types, ranking of social roles in the process of travel, as well as the study of travel as a form of escapism and stress resistance. Numerous works of foreign psychologists A. Adler, J. Adler, J. Crompton, R. Crandell, J. Dann, R. Calanton. Should It should be noted that these issues are interpreted by Western researchers mainly in the traditions of humanistic psychology and social psychology. A number of psychologists consider the problem of tourism in connection with research lifestyle, leisure, everyday culture. The psychologic researchers find that there are specific triggers, which contribute to or influence tourist well-being. Some of these triggers include the variables of happiness, positive emotions, savoring, character strengths, gratitude, humor, mindfulness, engagement, relationships, meaning and accomplishment[12]. A human behavior is in focus of many tourism researchers, also they pay attention to tourists, their connection of choice, destination, spending and next choice they will have. These aspects can be found in the research of these following scientists.

Economic psychology of tourism Crotts and Raaij (1994)[3], modelling of tourism impacts of Dyer et al. (2007)[5], tourists' leisure activities, consumption systems, decision and choice of Crouch et al. (2004)[4], tourist motivation in relation to the market segmentation of Dolnicar and Leisch (2004)[15] and also in residents' attitudes towards tourism impacts of Aref (2010)[1], tourism and quality of life of Uysal (2012)[11].[10]

The assessment of the tourism potential of the region's resources depends on geographical factors. The science of **geography and archeology** – natural-climatic, demographic data, trends and prospects of their change, detailed planning of interregional and intraregional development of tourism, planning the development of objects, tourism industry, investment in the tourism sector,

tourist flows, population employment, and income from tourism It is essential for income planning. At the current stage of development, any branch of the economy cannot work without strong information support. **Information technology** on various scientific fields is also used for tourism purposes. Today, various automated information systems play an important role in booking tourist services. Information on tourist resources, tourist products is available in various forms of calculations, references, catalogs, prospectuses, road signs, tables, timetables.

Many tourist companies have not only a private tourist agency, but also powerful information centers and publishers. For example, the UK travel agency Reed Travel Group is an example of this. It should be noted that guidebooks were developed long before the development of tourism itself. When Thomas Cook first organized a tourist trip, there were guide books for making the journey from London to Paris. Most road signs are 100 years old. The global network of the Internet has become another great impetus for the development of tourism information. Today, almost all tourist companies have access to this network through their websites and e-mail. All users of the network have the opportunity to get a wide range of information about tourist services.

Figure 2. The connection between Tourism and psychology

Government organizations responsible for tourism, private companies, tourism firms, hotels, tourism associations, carriers, companies offering attraction services have large information sheets. Placing information on the Internet is generally cheaper than publishing a book or booklet, changes the appearance of information easily and quickly, and can also transmit high-quality color illustrated information. Information reaches a wide range of users in developed countries.

Tourism, as an important part of the economy of most countries, as part of **international relations**, requires special legal regulation. That's why a unique network – **tourism law** has been created. In most countries, basic concepts of tourism activity norms and development principles for resident and non-resident companies are strengthened by national laws on tourism. There are usually certain restrictions on the activities of non-residents. Relations between tourism organizers and tourist-clients are regulated. When it comes to **marketing and management** these fields has following tasks in the terms of tourism trade:

Figure 3. Relationship of marketing and tourism[7]

Learning from many scientists works, it is clear that how tourism trade is connected to various sciences, importance of tourism application in one country effects not only economic potentials, but also other different fields and industries too. Whether is economy or not improvement in tourism trade gives many results, increasing revenue of country's budget, employment places, discovery of new cultural resorts and extra flow of money in the market.

Conclusion

Learning tourism trade as the phenomenon of different fields helps to understand the importance of tourism industry, how tourists behavior relates to their choice. Different fields open up various dimensions of tourism trade helping to make strategies, tactics and managing models. Psychological aspects of tourism helps to understand why one tourist chooses a specific country while others choose different one, why age group, social life, locals' behavior impacts tourism export and import. All together helps to make specific and appropriate strategy to one country if this country is willing to increase tourism trade for a long time.

Learning tourism trade as different fields' phenomenon we can achieve following:

1. enhancement of visitor satisfaction which may involve recognition that social carrying capacities are less than the physical carrying capacities;
2. acceptance that a growth in visitor numbers is inconsistent with the objectives of maintaining environments and tourist satisfaction;
3. more careful marketing of an attraction in the sense of matching tourist zone with types of tourists and their needs;
4. the establishment of alternative criteria of success, so that mere numbers of tourists are not seen as the goal of tourism marketing, but rather the achievement of high rates of satisfaction [9].

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